

A simple and novel method of quantifying the effect of drought stress on spikelet sterility during the reproductive stage in rice

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Rice is most sensitive to drought during the reproductive stage, especially at flowering. This is manifested by a sharp increase in the number of sterile spikelets. In a strict sense, sterile spikelets are spikelets that failed to get fertilized during pollination. However, this is also the general term used for spikelets that failed to form into full-grain size. Previous studies suggest that spikelet sterility is mainly caused by the compounding effect of failure in panicle exertion (Ekanayake et al 1989, O'Toole and Namuco 1983). However, no concrete evidence shows how much of the failure in grain formation is contributed by drought stress in each developmental stage occurring in the spikelet during and after pollination. This study will provide a simple and novel method of quantifying the effect of drought stress on spikelet development to elucidate accurately the most sensitive stage during rice flowering.

This experiment was conducted in the IRRI greenhouse in 2005 and 2006. Ten selected genotypes, which are popularly grown by farmers in Asia, were used: IR64 (Philippines, Indonesia, Vietnam), IR36 (India, Indonesia), IR66 (Cambodia), BR11 (Bangladesh), KDML 105 (Thailand, Laos), Mahsuri (India), RD 6 (Thailand, Laos), Swarna (India), Samba Mahsuri (India), and Theedat Yin (Myanmar; Narciso and Hossain 2002). Drought stress was imposed 3 d before heading (DBH) and plants were rewatered after reaching 40–55% of leaf relative water content. The plants were grown to maturity and unfilled grains were separated from filled grains.

The unfilled grains were dissected under a stereomicroscope or through the aid of a table-type illuminator. Using spikelets harvested at maturity is an advantage as it allows researchers to get a more accurate estimate by eliminating bias in sample collection and by getting a sufficient number of spikelets to analyze, enough to represent the effect of stress at the whole-plant level. Using this method, sterile spikelets can be categorized into six groups, representing the stages in spikelet development affected by the stress (see figure). These are stage 1 – spikelets that failed to reach full grain size (immature spikelets) and the

following spikelets that reached full grain size but failed to proceed to the subsequent step for grain formation; stage 2 – spikelets with anthers at the middle and filaments that failed to elongate; stage 3 – spikelets with elongated filament but with anthers that failed to exert; stage 4 – spikelets with exerted anthers but no ovary enlargement; stage 5 – spikelets with enlarged ovary but no starch filling; and stage 6 – spikelets with incomplete grain filling. Stages 1–4 represent the events happening at the prefertilization stage, whereas stages 5 and 6 represent the events after fertilization.

The results showed that sterile spikelets in the majority of the rice genotypes tested (see table) were most sensitive at stage 4 (anthers exerted but no ovary enlargement) in well-watered conditions, with a significant increase under drought conditions. The number of stage 3 sterile spikelets (with elongated filament but no anther exertion) in most of the varieties also increased significantly under drought. This information can be a useful guide in determining the effect of other abiotic stresses such as heat, cold, and salinity and in uncovering the constitutive plant traits that can have an influence on overcoming the effect on these sensitive stages.

Effect of drought stress on the distribution of sterile spikelets in different developmental stages of Asia's most popular rice varieties.^a

Variety	Sterile spikelets (%)					
	Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4	Stage 5	Stage 6
Mahsuri	1 (1)	0 (1)	1 (8)	6 (21)	6 (10)	1 (1)
Samba Mahsuri	0 (0) ^b	7 (8)	3 (7)	8 (20)	4 (6)	4 (2)
IR64	0 (1)	0 (2)	1 (14)	8 (32)	1 (3)	2 (0)
RD 6	0 (1)	1 (2)	3 (10)	27 (38)	1 (1)	1 (0)
IR66	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (15)	7 (41)	0 (1)	0 (0)
Theedat Yin	0 (0)	0 (1)	2 (28)	12 (29)	2 (1)	1 (0)
KDML 105	1 (3)	3 (10)	13 (18)	40 (38)	0 (0)	0 (0)
IR36	1 (1)	0 (1)	2 (32)	8 (38)	1 (0)	1 (0)
Swarna	0 (1)	0 (12)	2 (37)	8 (23)	7 (1)	2 (1)
BR11	0 (0)	1 (22)	6 (38)	26 (25)	2 (3)	1 (0)

^aThe numbers represent the average sterile spikelets (expressed in %) in the two trials. The first number refers to sterile spikelets under well-watered conditions; the number in parentheses refers to those under drought-stressed conditions. ^bOne trial only.

Sterile spikelets at different stages of spikelet development: (A) stage 1, immature spikelets; (B) stage 2, spikelets with anthers just at the middle; (C) stage 3, spikelets with elongated filaments, anthers just below unopened lemma and palea; (D) stage 4, spikelets with exerted anthers but no ovary enlargement; (E) stage 5, spikelets with enlarged ovaries but not filled with starch; and (F) stage 6, spikelets with incomplete grain filling. All photos taken using Olympus SZX-7 stereomicroscope; magnification= 25X.

References

- Ekanayake IJ, Steponkus PL, de Datta SK. 1989. Spikelet sterility and flowering response of rice to water stress at anthesis. *Ann. Bot.* 63:257-264.
- Narciso J, Hossain M. 2002. World rice statistics (online). www.irri.org/science/ricestat (posted in 2002).
- O'Toole JC, Namuco OS. 1983. Role of panicle exertion in water stress-induced sterility. *Crop Sci.* 23:1093-1097.